

The Nature and Nurture of Language: A Review of Biological and Social Perspectives*

Dilin Doğası ve Gelişimi: Biyolojik ve Sosyal Perspektiflerin Değerlendirilmesi

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Abstract

The nature versus nurture debate is a central topic in psychology. It emphasizes the factors contributing to the development of personality, character, and language. In the context of language acquisition, the debate centers on biological factors such as the brain's specific regions versus social and environmental influences such as the family's mother tongue. Noam Chomsky is a key figure on the nature side and proposed the Language Acquisition Device hypothesis. In contrast, Lev Vygotsky represents the nurture perspective and argues for the critical role of social interactions and cultural context in language development. He created the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development to highlight how learning occurs. The paper investigates both of Chomsky's and Vygotsky's theories and compares their theories on language acquisition. Moreover, it evaluates their hypotheses against current research. The paper specifically examines the impact of socioeconomic status, cultural differences in interaction styles, and the complexity of language used in daily life. The current study points out relationships between memory, metacognition, and Theory of Mind (TOM) to comprehend language skills in both humans and nonhumans. As a result, this study highlights the importance of intuitive cognitive processes and social-gestural interactions in comprehending how language is acquired.

Keywords: Nature versus nurture, language acquisition, Noam Chomsky, Lev Vygotsky, metacognition.

Öz

Doğa mı yetiştirme mi tartışması psikolojide merkezi bir konudur. Kişilik, karakter ve dil gelişiminin nedenlerini vurgular. Dil edinimi bağlamında, tartışma beynin

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belirli bölgeleri gibi biyolojik faktörler ile ailenin ana dili gibi sosyal ve çevresel etkiler arasında odaklanır. Noam Chomsky, doğa tarafının önemli bir figürüdür ve Dil Edinimi Aygıtı hipotezini ortaya atmıştır. Buna karşılık, Lev Vygotsky, yetiştirilme perspektifini temsil eder ve dil gelişiminde sosyal etkileşimlerin ve kültürel bağlamın kritik rolünü savunur. Öğrenmenin nasıl gerçekleştiğini vurgulamak için Yakın Gelişim Alanı kavramını oluşturmuştur. Bu bildiri de hem Chomsky'nin hem de Vygotsky'nin teorilerini incelenmekte ve dil edinimi konusundaki teorileri karşılaştırılmaktadır. Ayrıca, mevcut araştırmalara göre hipotezleri değerlendirilmektedir. Özellikle sosyoekonomik durumun, etkileşim tarzlarındaki kültürel farklılıkların ve günlük yaşamda kullanılan dilin karmaşıklığının etkisini inceleyen çalışma hem insanlarda hem de insan olmayanlarda dil becerilerini anlamak için bellek, üstbilgi ve Zihin Teorisi arasındaki ilişkileri ortaya koymaktadır. Sonuç olarak, bu çalışma, dilin nasıl edinildiğini anlamada sezgisel bilişsel süreçlerin ve sosyal-jestsel etkileşimlerin önemini vurgulamaktadır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Doğa mı yetiştirme mi, dil edinimi, Noam Chomsky, Lev Vygotsky, metabilgi.

Introduction

The debate of nurture versus nature is a common study area in psychology. Researchers study it in several sub study areas of psychology, such as clinical psychology, cognitive psychology, and developmental psychology. In this debate, common sense is about the interaction between genes and social environments. The debate has been studied to reveal effects on cognition, decision-making, and language acquisition. Thus, theorists emphasize the role of environment, social context, genes, and components of character in shaping human behavior. For instance, research is commonly done on twin studies; thus, researchers analyze social environment, the effect of parenting, and social and genetic relations and fluencies. In cognitive psychology, psychologists focus on neural development and neuronal communication with limits of human cognition. So, they study understanding behavior's neural essentials and social interactions. Lastly, developmental psychologists investigate parenting in children and how parenting influences a child's development. They investigate plasticity as well, so they try to shed light on lifelong adaptation skills to new conditions (Stiles, 2011: 19-20; Belsky and Pluess, 2009: 347-348; Rutter, 1991: 126).

In the nurture versus nature debate, behaviorism and nativism are two different and opposite theories. While behaviorism represents nurture's importance as social context and receives input from social relations, nativism considers nature and its genes, character, and innate abilities as components. At this point, nativism defends the idea that people learn from their genes and inner knowledge coded in genes and biology. It suggests that human behavior depends on the influence of genes, biology, and inner processes. It gives more importance to innate learning and the intuitional process of human behavior, so they usually mention biological limitations and biological abilities. On the opposite side, behaviorism defends that a human's personality and behavior are shaped by social relations, social learning, and instructions from family, friends, school, and governments. Behaviorism argues that decisions are a consequence of learning, so it gives more importance to operant and conditional learning than nativism. At this point we mention Skinner and Pavlov. As importantly, behaviorism was represented by Skinner, Pavlov, and Vygotsky. On the other hand, nativism was represented by Chomsky (Zhao, 2022: 1226-1227; Dastpak, 2017: 231-233).

Chomsky argues that language acquisition abilities are innate and a subconscious process in humans. He emphasizes inner and external language, and thus expressive language abilities are intuitive. On the other hand, in behaviorism, Vygotsky reveals how children acquire language from the environment. He argues for the Zone of Proximal Development, and so he emphasizes that interaction with friends, family, and organizations creates language acquisition. Skinner and Pavlov have done research in learning and suggest learning language is a condition created by the environment (Alderson-Day & Fernyhough, 2015: 932; Dastpak, 2017: 233-234).

Current studies in language acquisition focus on social relations, cognition, learning abilities, socioeconomic state, and genes. For instance, FOXP2 was found to influence language learning in humans. People with genetic mutations in FOXP2 exhibit articulation difficulties. Beyond genetic factors, social roles and interactions with parents were found to have a positive relation to acquiring language. For instance, African Americans have lower interaction rates with their children than other groups. So, the children of Afro-Americans tend to speak less and have less word variation in sentences. Also, higher SES mothers talk more to their children than do

lower SES mothers when analysing social-economic status. In a comparison between low-SES, mid-SES, and high-SES families, results showed that higher-SES children hear more total words than the lower-SES children. As a result, we should consider both society's and genes' effect on language acquisition (Fisher, 2015: 14; Hoff, 2006: 60-63).

Finally, the review focuses on the Theory of Mind (TOM) and metacognition. The paper evaluates how these theories are associated with language, nature and nurture. Metacognition, the capacity for 'thinking about one's own thoughts', is considered by some researchers to be a uniquely human trait. Moreover, TOM is associated with understanding others' ideas and emotions; thus, language becomes more important for this process. The current paper compares these theories on humans and nonhumans to redefine cognition skills (Corballis, 2017: 232; Corballis, 2019: 2-4).

Nature Versus Nurture

The nature versus nurture debate is an old discussion topic in many disciplines. Nature corresponds to the effect of biology, genes, and intuitive processes, and nurture means how interaction affects our body and mind. For instance, people have brain plasticity, and thus people make new connections that are called neuronal wiring. Neural wiring helps us to make new neuron connections so we can gain new knowledge and reshape our brains to adapt to new conditions. However, we should emphasize the role of the critical period because of the changing plasticity abilities by age. Research has shown if one tapes one eye shut from birth, the mouse never gains the ability to see from that eye. However, if one tapes one eye of an adult mouse for a similar period, vision ability isn't affected (URL-1; Shonkoff and Phillips, 2000: 39).

In the debate, Plomin and Bergeman (1991: 375-382) investigate the role of socioeconomic status, education, peers, social support, life events, and television viewing. They shed light on genetic influences on the environmental measures. Thus, they aimed to show how the environment is shaped by the genetic influences. In addition, Shonkoff and Phillips (2000: 40-41) emphasize that we should rethink the interaction of nature and nurture. They suggest it is impossible to think of nature as separate from nurture. They argue we have to consider environmental conditions and genetic uniqueness together due to interaction. They reconceptualise the nature and nurture debate and argue nature through nurture. Moreover, they say

there is an interaction between nature and nurture, so they cannot think separately. Shonkoff and Phillips (2000: 47) express a way to study genetic and environmental conditions. They focus on shared and nonshared environments. According to that, in the shared environment, effects make individuals similar. In the nonshared environment, influences are those that distinguish among individuals in the same environment. For instance, divorcing is a nonshared and shared environment situation. It is a shared environmental influence due to all siblings experiencing it, but it is a non-shared environmental influence due to siblings experiencing it differently.

In spite of genetic factors on nurture, Britto et al. (2016: 91) have studied nurturing care. Nurturing care consists of behaviors, attitudes and knowledge regarding caregiving, stimulation and responsiveness. Early experiences shape the later years in adulthood, and adaptation skills are essential for that. The quality and quantity of the early experiences are associated with increased ability to learn, greater achievements in school and involvement in community activities. Early-year experiences are **influenced by** maternal health, mental disorders, parenting support, attachment and breastfeeding. Before the birth, if the mother uses tobacco or alcohol, it may cause a serious threat to the health of the pregnant mother and her children. Maternal nutrition has been found to affect health. For instance, during pregnancy, iron and iron-folate supplementation reduces the risk of premature births. Mental disorders and hormonal signals that happen due to stress may disrupt normal processes, so they can have negative effects on the foetus. Parents' supporting behaviors may help to acquire language, cognitive abilities, and motor development. Additionally, supportive attachment styles have a positive impact on learning, memory, and executive control. Lastly, breastfeeding has short-term benefits, and it helps to improve performance in intelligence tests in childhood and adolescence (Britto et al., 2016: 91-95). In summary, nurture contains attachment styles, nutrients, carer's behavior and mental conditions.

Noam Chomsky's Universal Grammar and Language Concept

Chomsky is a key figure in language theories due to arguing a new concept that is called "Universal Grammar". He assumes that language is not a kind of skill that can be learnt; it is an initial process. He revolutionizes the theory of learning language and argues that it is acquired. As an opposite assumption, he makes a new definition about the language not being

learnt as Skinner's hypothesis. In contrast of Skinner's learning methods, Chomsky argues language is an intuitive skill, and all humans have this capacity (Touqir et al., 2018: 2). During language acquisition, children can produce a limitless amount of sentences. Children can produce novel sentences they have never heard before. **This ability** is possible because humans possess an abstract system of unconscious linguistic knowledge. According to Chomsky's argument, children don't need to hear language. They acquire the language by genetic codes (Wen, 2013: 149-150). Exposure to language and not differences in language form are Chomsky's arguments. He conceptualized E-language and I-language to restrict external conditions. To make a better discrimination, Chomsky creates a distinction between spoken, perceptible language and internal language that reflects the human mind. For Chomsky, only I-language matters to study due to not being affected by external conditions. Additionally, he points out that I-language should be studied in isolation from external environments that make E-language (Barman, 2014: 115-116).

Beyond language's essentials for acquiring it, we consider language's basis for producing it biologically. As a bio linguistic approach, Chomsky's Language Acquisition Device depends on the assumption that language abilities are related to biological bases. Chomsky argues all people acquire language intuitively with Universal Grammar and assume all people have a Language Acquisition Device as well. Thus, all people have a special ability to acquire language by internal constraint and external environment. More specifically, the bio linguistics theory is shaped by three essential factors: universal grammar, experience and third factors. According to this approach, the initial stage of language learning is determined by our genetic endowment. Experience corresponds to the source of language variation. Lastly, third factors include principles not specific to the language (Yang et al., 2017: 104). As a result, we can consider Chomsky as a nativist and representative person on the nature side of the nature versus nurture debate. Zhao (2022: 1227) expresses that Chomsky is a figure in nativism.

The Biological Fundamentals of Language

Human language skills have genetic fundamentals. Investigations have shown FOXP2 gene deficits may cause articulation errors that are inconsistent. The KE family is the first that gets a diagnosis. They showed that deficits in the FOXP gene may be seen in relatives, and genetic factors are

key (Fisher, 2015: 14). However, the language deficits aren't limited to gene studies. Biologically, people acquire language abilities before birth. Human language abilities are seen in newborns and before the birth, as a foetus. Foetuses show the same brain activation to the sound as adults, so it proves humans are born with a language skill (Dehaene, 2020: 70).

The most known areas that are associated with language function are the Broca and Wernicke areas. Broca's area is located in the posterior inferior frontal gyrus. It is responsible for producing spoken language. Paul Broca, who found the area, discovered it and led the new researchers to the biological essentials of spoken language and how it is connected with mouth movements. The Broca area is located in Broadmann areas 44 and 45. It has a correlation with right-handedness. Right-handed individuals have a dominant left hemisphere mostly. As a deficit, Broca's aphasia may cause the loss of spoken language skills. They experience a deficit in writing and spoken language as well (URL-3). Additionally, the Wernicke area plays an important role in comprehending the language. It is located in the posterior section of the superior temporal gyrus. Similarly to the Broca area, language function localizes to the left cerebral cortex in the majority of right-handed people. For the majority of right-handed people, language functions are localized in the left hemisphere. It is important to note, however, that this is not unique to right-handers. Generally, left-handed people show the exact same brain asymmetry. Unlike Broca's aphasia, these patients have grammatical rules with normal sentence structure; however, comprehending complex sentences is hard for them. In addition, the impairment is limited in these cases (URL-2).

To investigate the biological aspects of language, researchers use technological methods. These are functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), electroencephalography (EEG), and positron emission tomography (PET). All of them have their own features to measure brain activation. For instance, Dehaene-Lambertz, Hertz-Pannier, and Dubois (2006: 368-372) use fMRI to investigate the reaction of babies to sounds. They found infant brains showed an activation in the superior temporal gyrus by using fMRI. Additionally, the article emphasizes the distinguished language skills between humans and animals. In the research, they found that asymmetry is not special for humans, and monkeys have it too. They have confirmed that

monkeys' brains showed a left-lateralized activation when they heard own-species vocalizations by using PET.

The Social Basis of Human Language and the Role of Vygotsky

Hoff (2006: 57) and Tomasello (1992: 67) emphasize the role of language in comprehending it and express that environmental support is necessary for language development. For instance, North American mothers are prone to talk more to their babies from the birth. Unlike them, in some cultures, like the Mayans of Mexico, mothers don't perceive babies as potential conversational partners. However, it is not an impediment to comprehending language for babies. So, it shows evidence for a universal basis for language skills (Hoff, 2006: 59). Additionally, when comparing the cultural differences, a variation has been found. When comparing Asian and North American mothers, it has been found that North American mothers probably use more nouns in their sentences. In the opposite way, Asian mothers are prone to use more verbs in their sentences (Hoff, 2006: 59).

Kinzler, Dupoux, and Spelke (2007: 12579) did research to determine the social cognition of babies and how they make a choice between various languages. They made an experiment to see whether babies take toys from their mother language or other languages. The findings showed infants in Paris are prone to reach for the toy offered by the French speaker. Similarly, infants in Boston showed reaching movement to the toys offered by English speakers. The choosing toy behavior is a sign for social cognition. It is another proof of how environmental conditions shape human behavior.

As Vygotsky has mentioned before, human social behaviour is shaped by environmental conditions (Dastpak, 2017: 234). Vygotsky shed light on the types of speech and argues children have two different speech styles in their lives that they use at different times and in various conditions. The first of them is called egocentric speech, which serves a function in articulation. Children talk to themselves while engaged in a cognitive task. Children use it for self-regulation and develop a strategy for their behaviors and cognition skills. Most studies point to the fact that egocentric speech is universal. Additionally, Vygotsky developed egocentric speech by getting inspiration from Watson's behaviorism. The second speech is communicative speech. It happens in the late years of childhood, and children perform it for social interaction (Alderson-Day & Fernyhough, 2015: 932; Dastpak, 2017: 234).

To explain the social dynamics and the role of the language, Vygotsky argues a theory that is called “The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)”. According to this theory, children have three dimensions in communication. Stages are divided into three. The first circle is children’s to-do things by themselves; they can do it without getting help from the parents. The second circle covers the first one and corresponds to that to do things by getting help from the environment. And the last circle covers all of them, and it means children cannot succeed in that even if they get help. Vygotsky emphasizes the environmental conditions and language’s role in there (Fani and Ghaemi, 2011: 1551; Dastpak, 2017: 234).

Inner speech is a function to regulate cognition and behaviors for children. They use it for better communication and to express themselves. In this way, it shows a metacognition sign (Alderson-Day and Fernyhough, 2015: 933). As mentioned before, Kinzler, Dupoux, and Spelke (2007: 12579) found babies can detect different voices and show diverse toy choices. Also, they found babies prone to look into faces of people who speak their mother language. It is a metacognition skill; thus, babies can detect different sounds from each other. The behavior of deciding for something in the babies is important in ZPD. To choose to get help or evaluate that the baby can do it means there are high cognitive abilities.

Metacognition and Language Skills

There are diverse approaches to studying language and its uniqueness. The association between language and thought is not clear; however, it is a fact that our thoughts and words are different. It generally seems to be in translation and cultural differences. A perfect 1-to-1 translation of a word is often not possible. Because the underlying meaning of a thought is tied to its cultural context, some meaning is almost always lost during translation. To study that, mental travel time and the theory of mind come to the forefront (Corballis, 2017: 231-232; Corballis, 2019: 2).

Mental time travel is a function to conceptualize a nonpresent time. It makes it possible to refer to a place and time that will happen or has already happened. To make that, the species requires having a consciousness for the past and future. Tulving argues it is unique for humans, and they perform it because of language skills. He links it with memory and emphasizes the role of memory types for mental time travel. According to his studies, there are three different thought styles. These are autothetic thought, that

is, consciousness of personal experience; noetic thought, that is, awareness of the word; and lastly, anoetic thought, which corresponds to automatic activities. Only auto-noetic thought is special and unique for humans. Noetic and anoetic thoughts are found in nonhuman animals as well. Tulving argues mental time travel is a unique feature of human language because of having an episodic memory that helps to think about ourselves that links to auto-noetic thought. He examines the role of the hippocampus in recalling information from the past or imagining the future. The relation between language and memory depends on mental time travel. Thus, humans express the nonpresent events by using the language and make social connections. It is clear there is an association between biological factors and social behaviors (Corballis, 2019: 2-4). The other approach to studying mind and language is Theory of Mind (TOM). 'Theory of Mind' means having a capacity to understand others' minds by getting help from language. Words reflect humans' minds, so having a word to point to a situation is essential for understanding others'. It is a sign for metacognition due to requiring a high cognitive skill such as thinking about what they think now as well (Corballis, 2017: 232).

Terrace (2005: 85) emphasises the role of language on non-humans. Not surprisingly, communication is not special for humans, and other creatures have their own communication styles. The most fascinating experiments are studied on chimpanzees, gorillas, orangutans, and bees. A divergence in language skills **exists** between humans and nonhumans because of metacognitive skills. Human language has its own unique aspects and differs from nonhumans' languages. For instance, Project Nim was a project to observe a chimpanzee's language abilities. This male chimpanzee acquired more than 20,000 combinations of two or more signs. There is support from the evidence due to growing up with a human family as well. The other study is made on Kanzi, a young male bonobo chimpanzee. Kanzi was able to understand lexigrams by observational learning and did it rapidly without any formal training. Surprisingly, Kanzi was able to comprehend the spoken language. He could carry out a command such as "put the collar in the water". He showed an intelligence that equals that of a child of two or three years old (Terrace, 2005: 85-104).

Beyond the animal researchers, it is clear apes are able to comprehend symbols that are related to diverse awards, but they don't use this capacity

to share information. Sharing information requires joint attention. There are two different ways for joint attention. These are called protoimperative and protodeclarative pointing. The first of them is included in humans, and humans, however, protodeclarative pointing is not included in nonhumans. Protoimperative pointing is used to point to something that represents a desire by someone; protodeclarative pointing is used by someone to share an experience and knowledge. For instance, pointing to a cookie as a request is a protoimperative pointing behavior, and if a child points to a cat to direct a parent, it means it is protodeclarative pointing behavior. Despite babies getting better at protodeclarative pointing by age, nonhuman primates cannot show this kind of behavior. So, it creates a distance between nonhuman primates and humans on metacognition (Terrace, 2005: 85-104).

Conclusion

On the nature side, genetic studies on FOXP2 and anatomical findings from the Broca and Wernicke areas support the nature of language acquisition. These findings are correlated with Chomsky's arguments, especially I-language. I-language creates a divergence between humans and nonhumans. So, all of these make up the nature aspect of the language and the "hardware" of the language. On the other hand, the nurture side, socioeconomic status (SES), parental support and a rich environment play a crucial role in how language is acquired. The nurture side points out that social bases are necessary for language, and Vygotsky is an important figure in this perspective. He explains how children use language to communicate and socialize. Behaviorism is generally considered the foundation of nurture, while nativism considers the foundation of nature. Both of them showed strong evidence to shed light on language functions and features. Specifically, metacognition and Theory of Mind (TOM) studies have focused on language forms between creatures and try to figure out language capabilities between them. To achieve that, researchers used both social and biological concepts. As a result, the review concludes that language has a special context that cannot be understood in isolation from the integrated effects of both nature and nurture.

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